

Gender Based Marginality: Suppression and Oppression in Arthur Miller's Broken Glass

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This paper focuses on Miller's impact on the suppression of female character in Broken Glass. The play was written in the decade of nineties and forms a kind of continuum- the common theme of dysfunctional marriage and family is at the core of the play. The woman character is again represented in a negative way, in the play. Miller is concerned here with the paralysis of a nation or an individual conscience in face of increasing anti- Semitism in Europe and America. Broken Glass, set in Brooklyn in November 1938, is a two act play that explores the themes of sexual awakening, the result of denial and effect of social injustice on an individual.

According to Murray Biggs, Broken Glass (1994) is a study of both those psychologies: the impulse to ignore what is happening and the refusal to admit that it did happen. The play's whole thrust is in fact psychological at least as much as political. Philip and Sylvia Gellberg are joined by race and marriage; yet divided by both. He seeks to suppress his Jewishness, she to embrace it. He is sexually dysfunctional, she sexually unsatisfied what Hymen diagnoses as her hysterical paralysis with its source in her unconscious, is an effect of both these divisions.

The three important characters are Philip Gellburg, his wife and Doctor Hyman. The play shows the institution of marriage. Philip Gillberg is an executive and the only Jew working in a wall street Bank. His wife is obsessed with Nazi Germany. When she sees a photograph of old Jewish men scrubbing the sidewalk with toothbrushes, she becomes suddenly paralyzed in the legs. Dr. Hyman is perhaps the only person who sympathetically understands the plight of this long suffering homemaker, her fears and longings. Dr. Hyman is shown as highly passionate person, whose counterfoil becomes Philip who is very repressed by the system. The usual issues of denial and social injustice are linked with sexual awakening in the refined and well aware Sylvia who has been a timid and quiet woman for more than thirty years of her married life. In fact, the system does not allow her private space and makes her conform to the traditional role of a dutiful and obedient wife. A feminist reading of the play reveals the plight of woman like Sylvia trapped in a loveless cold marriage.

Sylvia represents the repressed female sexuality that is dreaded by the male centered, conservative money driven society. As usual, the focus of the play is largely upon the two male characters. Sylvia just happens to be a secondary prop to them.

The Broken Glass has two types of Women, Sylvia and Margaret. Sylvia is meek and dominated by her abusive and controlling husband. She does not find any fulfillment in her married life. She has been forced to suppress her real feelings and sexual desires in order to save her marriage of convenience. She does this sacrifice for the larger good of her parental family that is dependent on Philip. Margaret is the opposite: vivacious, active and perceptive, keeping an eye on the extra-marital relationship of a philandering husband.

In the play, the paralyzed Sylvia comes to discover her suppressed sexuality and other desires, in fact, her identity as a woman through the sympathetic doctor Hyman who praises her and her body in very flattering terms. This praise makes her aware of her own body, her desires and dreams. She has been long suppressed and neglected in her marital home. Doctor Hyman offers her sympathy, understanding and love. In the end Sylvia is taunted by her suspicious husband and made to stand up, which she does finally gets the courage and overcomes her initial guilt. Even Margaret and Doctor Hyman are pleasantly shocked to see this sudden change in an otherwise quiet and silently enduring Sylvia. For twenty years, as suggested in the play, Sylvia could not get intimate pleasure from her husband, thus forcing herself to a life of a nun in her own house. But Doctor Hyman changes all that. She is no longer in denial about her body and her suppressed sexuality. She finds her release before her collapsed husband and feels liberated by that sight of her fallen tormentor.

The Holocaust and its terrible images of persecution of the Jews leaves her paralyzed but in the end, her will to live and find meaning in life makes her come out of her hysterical paralysis. The collapsed Philip and an encouraging Hyman trigger her recovery. Seen this way, from a feminist angle, Sylvia becomes a symbol of recovery from oppression. She finds her freedom and reclaims her sexuality in those final moments of confrontation with her husband. The Play Broken Glass, on a feminist reading reveals the role of sexuality in the release and liberation of an oppressed woman. Glass is to be broken by somebody and Sylvia does it in this play. As usual, the playwright focuses more on the male characters than the female ones. His sympathies are with the male viewpoint only. Women although on marginality forms common emotional lexicon of disillusionment, pain, humiliation and rejection that enables them to arrive at a better understanding of themselves and their psyches.

Thus, Women are the other in Arthur Miller's theatrical world. They are powerless, suppressed and subordinated by the patriarchal system that has got precedence over the class structure in the advanced capitalist model called America, the very citadel of democratic rights. Women, however are the second sex, despite the political rhetoric. Women and marginality go together in the artistic world of Arthur Miller.

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